

THE PROBLEMS OF MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN UNIVERSITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716175>

ANNOTATSIIYA

The article considers the problems various methods of teaching foreign languages in universities. Particular attention was paid to the following methods: direct method, grammar-translation, audiovisual, audiolingual and communicative. According to the author modern teaching methods involve the use of such a system of methods, which is aimed not at the presentation of ready-made knowledge by the teacher and their reproduction, but at the independent mastery of knowledge by the trainees in the process of active cognitive activity.

Key words: activities, audiovisual, audiolingual, communicative, communication, development, direct, education, English, foreign, language, method, modern, process, skill, system, teaching

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются проблемы различных методик обучения иностранным языкам в вузах. Особое внимание уделялось следующим методам: прямому методу, грамматико-переводному, аудиовизуальному, аудиолингвальному и коммуникативному. По мнению автора, современные методы обучения предполагают использование такой системы методов, которая направлена не на изложение учителем готовых знаний и их воспроизведение, а на самостоятельное овладение знаниями обучаемыми в процессе обучения. активная познавательная деятельность.

Ключевые слова: деятельность, аудиовизуальный, аудиолингвальный, коммуникативный, общение, развитие, непосредственное, образование, английский язык, иностранный, язык, метод, современный, процесс, умение, система, обучение

INTRODUCTION

Education is a one of the most important activities in people's life. Students master their talents and skills during studying time. Teachers are connecting links in this process and it is essential to give special attention to their training. The one of the main problems of modern education is interaction and intercommunication between teachers and students. It is important to find a right approach to every student to make educational process convenient. "All people vary with their behavioral and emotional peculiarities which are closely connected with character. A proficient teacher should

consider everyone's peculiarities" [1]. Therefore, teachers need to have peculiar skills to be able to determine personality characteristics define specific approaches in the educational process. In this context consistent methods of education should be developed to improve the process of education. The needs of our state for highly qualified specialists capable of establishing business contacts and business cooperation with foreign partners, professionals who speak a foreign language at a professional level, are reflected in the working curricula of universities in the country. Today, a foreign language is not just a part of the culture of a certain nation, but it is also the key to success, the future successful career of students. "Achieving a high level of proficiency in a foreign language is impossible without fundamental language training in higher education. At most universities in the country, students master at least two foreign languages" [2]. Modern ways of educating English have enhanced in the last twenty years. Nowadays everything alters, obviously in teaching the English language. As a matter of fact, there is an enormous variability of strategies of teaching foreign languages to language learners. Today the process of English learning will be more student – centered, but less time consuming. Therefore, we should use the modern methods in teaching a foreign language. The modern teaching methods help to build or develop a productive understanding of basic science and technology. Hence, the elements of contemporary teaching methods include: Currently, there are many methods for learning a foreign language in higher educational institutions. Each of the methods has certain features, some are more popular and in demand, some less. This article will discuss the main methods for students to learn English. In the modern world, English is very popular, moreover, this language is the language of international communication, it is known all over the world. Today, there are a huge number of methods for teaching English. In addition, new ones are regularly developed, so now every teacher can choose the most suitable method of work for himself. Currently, when teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions, classical methods are most often used. Namely: 1. Direct method. 2. Grammar-translation teaching method. 3. Audiovisual and audio lingual methods. 4. Communicative method. In this article, we will look at each of these techniques in more detail.

METHODS

During writing of the this article we have used the following research method: analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature on the problems of the modern teaching methods. Direct method of teaching a foreign language is that the teacher pays more attention to the study of directly spoken language, which is used in everyday life. The developers of this method considered that the intermediary

language, that is, the language in which teaching is conducted, slows down the learning of a foreign language. Thus, students are artificially introduced into the world of the language they are learning. “The entire lesson is conducted in English, the teacher must also give explanations and new topics in English” [3]. Only English-language literature is used. When teaching English using this method, the role of the teacher in the successful assimilation of knowledge by students is key. “That is, his speech must be absolutely clear and correct, the pronunciation must be perfect, since the students will constantly repeat exactly after the teacher. The ideal option for a direct teaching method would be to make a native English teacher [4]”. Grammar-translation method Grammar-translation method is the main one in the modern education system. This is a classic method that has been used for decades. Its prevalence is also due to the fact that most of the teachers themselves trained using this method. “The purpose of the grammar-translation method is to learn to read and translate using grammar rules. the grammar-translation (traditional) method was used in foreign language lessons in the days of the. The students were offered a text that they read to the chain” [5]. This was followed by a translation as close as possible to the text, the grammatical structure was memorized without taking into account the context and possible situations of its application in real communication.

RESULTS

Researching on this topic I have come to the following results. The students memorized long lists of words, “topics”, and they studied the foreign language as if it were dead, because the average citizen of the would hardly have had the opportunity to communicate with a foreigner. The teachers did not set themselves the goal of teaching them to speak a foreign language, since there was no such need. Thus, almost the entire lesson was held in Uzbek. Ultimately, all that school graduates could do was read and translate with a dictionary. Also, as a result of applying the traditional method, children have a huge language barrier, and full confidence is formed that they are unable to learn a foreign language. This is not surprising, because in this case, students do not master foreign language speech, but only receive certain information about it. Despite the large number of shortcomings of the grammar-translation method, it also has its advantages. Often, translating a word is the fastest way to explain its meaning. At the initial level of learning a foreign language, it is sometimes useful to use native speech when explaining grammatical rules. Plus, it saves a lot of time. Even a teacher who is not fluent in the language himself can teach a foreign language using the traditional method. However, in order to learn how to communicate with native speakers, it is not enough to be able to read and master grammar rules. It is very important to acquire certain skills, which

include, in addition to reading and writing, also speaking and listening (listening). “To speak a language means to think in it” [5]. Unfortunately, this cannot be achieved using the traditional method. Benefits of the “Direct Method: learning a foreign language in a natural way, 80% of the lesson you speak a foreign language, start practicing right away, get rid of the language barrier in communication, actively use vocabulary, learn enough grammar to express yourself correctly, minimum homework, no cramming, there is multiple repetition and practice, correct pronunciation [6]. The disadvantages of this method include the fact that insufficient attention is paid to the lexical part. The study of vocabulary is reduced to the mechanical memorization of words. Reading and translation is done in a strict manner. In addition, the texts offered for reading usually refer to Complex fiction, therefore, the student studies only the literary language. Once in the language environment, it will be very difficult for him to understand others even with a good knowledge of the literary language. Audiovisual and audiolingual methods The essence of both methods is to transfer the language through clear structures, memorization occurs with the help of audio and video recordings. The audiovisual teaching method involves illustrating speech with appropriate pictures, that is, students are shown videos, feature films and documentaries in English. In this case, the trainees work simultaneously with two channels of perception - visual and auditory, as a result of which associations arise in the students' head, which allows them to better memorize the language. “The purpose of the methods is to master a living, spoken language” [6].

DISCUSSION

All methods are based on induction - learning proceeds from a rule to an example. “Considering all of the above, it can be noted that for university students who do not specialize in language learning, audiolingual and audiovisual methods are suitable only if they are used in combination with other training programs” [7]. The audio-lingual teaching method is one of the most popular methods of learning foreign languages. Most often it is used by those who intend to independently learn a particular foreign language. Although in the pedagogical environment, it has its popularity. To understand what the audiolingual method of language learning is, I suggest referring to the dictionary entry. “The dictionary of methodological terms says that the audiolingual teaching method is a method of teaching a foreign language, which provides for the use of the auditory perception channel and repeated listening and playing after the speaker of strictly selected structures, sample sentences, which leads to their automation. If from an academic point of view we

understand what it is, then let's look at this method from a practical point of view and find all its pros and cons “[7]. How is the audiolingual method so different from traditional ways of learning a language? The first and main distinguishing feature of the audiolingual method is the assignment of oral speech to a paramount role in learning. The second feature is the enormous load on the student's memory and the method of analogy. The student must memorize (memorize) the main set of sentences that are most often used in colloquial speech. By analogy with these sentences, the student will build other sentences for oral reproduction or listening. It is also recommended to memorize entire dialogues and communicative situations. At the initial stage of training, the student's vocabulary practically does not develop. A small set of words is used, which allows you to work out the basic grammatical structures through speech and repetition-pronunciation. The third feature of the audiolingual method is a huge amount of practice. Only 15% of the lesson time is allocated for the explanation of grammatical, lexical, phonetic foundations. The rest of the time is devoted to practical exercises. However, such classes can quickly bore the student with their monotony and uniformity of approach. Therefore, it is recommended to immediately evaluate the actions of the student - did it right - praise, wrong -correct. The fourth feature is the dictionary. The audiolingual method divides words into categories of different difficulty levels with its own subgroups in each. The easiest include prepositions, adverbs, conjunctions, interrogative particles, articles. To the most difficult - words denoting objects, words denoting actions, words denoting quality, that is, nouns, adjectives and verbs. “Vocabulary is taught according to the principle from simple to complex. However, at the initial stage of learning, words from a complex category are used, but are selected in such a way that their form and meaning correspond as much as possible to the equivalents of the native language’ [8]. Everything here is just straight to disgrace. You have a set of words, pictures, cards, and building blocks that you repeatedly listen to and match to get a phrase by clicking on them or dragging them. Nothing complicated. Training always takes place according to the same scenario. First you see a set of words, voice acting and pictures for them, usually no more than 2-3 words are given per lesson. Then you work out these words by choosing a translation, writing, speaking, constantly listening and repeating aloud. Each card is voiced, so you will hear one word or expression many, many times. So you won't be able to remember. Later on, there is a complication. New words are added and phrases are expanded. They become more extensive and complex. If you had the phrase "The girl drinks milk", then after a couple of sessions this phrase turns into "The little girl drinks milk on the roof. There is no need to talk about convenience. You can practice when it's convenient for you. Even if the urge to

repeat English pronouns hits you at midnight, please just download the app.. Where an experienced teacher would have already offered you to read a magazine article that is interesting for you or discuss your taste preferences, then you continue to "roll your" snowball. And this is what often begins to tire and reduce motivation up to its complete absence.

CONCLUSION

A feature of the direct method is the repeated repetition by students of speech structures, speech samples, imitation of the teacher's speech, imitation of examples from the textbook. From practical examples, students come to an understanding of the rule, a particular grammatical phenomenon. Thus, students learn the language, relying not on strictly memorized rules, but on their own intuition, which implies greater memorization efficiency, success in comprehending the laws of the language. A significant amount of classes is devoted to speaking, which is understood and planned not as a repetition or simulation of dialogues, but as a conscious activity, for example, in a discussion, in the ability to express and prove one's point of view. The role of the teacher is growing: he becomes a model for linguistic imitation - his speech should be clear, correct, understandable. The teacher aims to work on the pronunciation of foreign students, to eradicate their accent. Most modern Russian language textbooks for foreign students, overcoming tradition, are built on the principles of the direct method - there is no detailed statement of the rules, attention is paid to speech situations, communication practice, memorizing clichés. The paragraph is built not according to the topic (family, home, study, etc.), or, for example, on a consistent presentation of the Russian case system, but according to the speech intention (to request information, write a letter. This technique assumes a greater activity of students, opens up wide opportunities for communication between the teacher and students. Classes are built according to an interactive methodology - dialogue exercises, situations of verbal communication, role-playing games, work in small groups, design are used. However, the method has disadvantages - increased attention to speaking reduces the development of other types of speech activity, such as reading and writing. It is impossible to completely deny the use of the native language of students, which is necessary as a basis for comparison, correction of errors, creation of an atmosphere of intercultural dialogue in the student audience. Therefore, the direct method is usually successfully used in combination with other methods.

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